

Artificial Intelligence and Social Networks for Early Detection of Depression

Abstract

Background

Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) or depression is among the most prevalent psychiatric disorders, affecting more than 300 million people worldwide. Early detection is critical for rapid intervention, which can potentially reduce the escalation of the disorder.

Objective

This study used data from social media networks to explore various methods of early detection of MDDs based on analysis with artificial intelligence.

Methods

Our best performing method is based on a dual approach that uses a machine learning model to detect depressed subjects and another model to identify non-depressed individuals.

Results

The results of a thorough evaluation of the method following a time-aware approach that rewards early detections demonstrate that the dual model can improve current state-of-the-art detection models by more than 10%.

Conclusions

Given the results, we consider that this work can help in the development of new solutions to deal with the early detection of depression on social networks.

Keywords: Depression; MDD; social media; early detection; artificial intelligence; machine learning

Introduction

Background

Major Depressive Disorder (MDD), also known simply as depression, is among the most prevalent psychiatric disorders globally [1,2]. As described in the World Health Organization's (WHO) Comprehensive Mental Health Action Plan 2013-2020 [3], depression alone affects more than 300 million people worldwide and is one of the largest single causes of disability worldwide, particularly for women. Depression currently accounts for 4.3% of the global burden of disease, and it is expected to be the leading cause of disease burden in high-income countries by 2030 [4].

The Institute of Medicine (IOM) Committee on the Prevention of Mental Disorders identified depression as the most preventable disorder [5], and several studies have

demonstrated that early recognition and treatment of depression can improve the negative impacts of the disorder [6-8]. Therefore, it is vital to provide an early identification of subjects suffering from depression in order to intervene as soon as possible and maximize the public health impact by potentially reducing disease escalation. However, provisions and services for the early detection and treatment of depression and other mental health disorders remain limited. Most diagnoses are formed on the basis of self- or family reports, and there are no validated, laboratory tested scales to detect or predict depression.

In this context, researchers are increasingly examining the potential of social media networks as tools to predict depression and detect its symptoms as manifested in user comments and related activities. Social networks such as Twitter, Facebook and Reddit have become part of our daily lives as media through which to share our thoughts, feelings and overall emotional status. As such, these platforms have become valuable data banks for marketers and researchers, who can analyze user metrics, shared content and related information to identify preferences and tastes, as well as other attitudes and behaviors [9]. For example, Reddit is an open-source platform where community members can submit content and vote on submissions. Content entries are organized by areas of interest (denoted as subreddits), with a large history of previous submissions covering several years. This social network is particularly interesting for our work, as it contains substantive content about different medical conditions, including MDD.

This study uses publicly available data from social networks to examine the effectiveness of different methods that can provide an early detection of major depressive disorders based on artificial intelligence. As detailed in the next sections, we mainly focus on two different methods, both of which are based on machine learning algorithms that use textual and semantic similarity features along with writing features (WF) to predict a subject's depression condition. The first technique follows a simpler proposal using a single machine learning algorithm, whereas the second model follows a dual approach. We conducted a thorough evaluation of each model following a time-aware approach that rewards early detections and considers late detections as false negatives. Our results show that the dual model can improve state-of-the-art detection models up to 10%. Furthermore, our methods were implemented using freely available tools, thus facilitating the reproduction of our research work [10].

The structure of the article is as follows. In Section 2, we examine related works concerning early detection of depression with a particular focus on techniques that use information extracted from social networks. Section 3 provides a detailed data analysis of the social network content for MDD detection. Section 4 describes our proposed model for the early detection of depression and Section 5 presents the results and performance improvements obtained over the state-of-the-art baselines. Finally, Section 6 summarizes our conclusions and future works in this line of research.

Related works

Several previous works have highlighted the importance of early detection in improving outcomes related to major depressive disorder [6-8]. Halfin's study demonstrated that the early detection, intervention and appropriate treatment can promote remission and reduce the emotional and financial burdens of this disease, and Picardi et al. [7] observed significant improvements in depressive symptoms and quality of life among subjects who had undergone early screening. Rost et al. [8] found that early intervention for depression can improve employee productivity and reduce absenteeism.

Over the past decade, social networks have increasingly become a focus of research efforts to identify and characterize the incidence of various disorders. For example, Prieto et al. [11] proposed a method to use Twitter to automatically measure the incidence of a set of health conditions. Chunara et al. [12] analyzed cholera-related tweets published during the first 100 days of the 2010 Haitian cholera outbreak, and Chew and Eysenbach [13] used sentiment analysis on two million tweets to propose a complementary intelligence approach.

Diverse studies have explored the potential of social media networks to predict and detect mental health disorders [14-18]. For example, De Choudhury et al. [17] developed a statistical marker to derive distinct markers of shifts to suicidal ideation from Reddit user data for modelling in a prediction framework, and Birnbaum et al. [15] proposed a method that used machine learning in combination with clinical appraisals as a means of identifying social media markers of schizophrenia.

Other studies have focused specifically on depression. Ziemer and Korkmaz's [19] comparison of human vs. automated text analyses of psychological and physical disorders found human ratings of depression to be more accurate than machine based methods; however, other studies have yielded promising, albeit limited results using sophisticated technological applications in detecting and measuring the disorder. Nadeem's "bag of words" analysis of Twitter messages [20] examined the frequency of use of "my" and "me" as a marker for depression, while De Choudhury et al. [9] leveraged social activity, emotion, and language signals manifested on Twitter to introduce a social media depression index. Similarly, a task organized at the CLPsych 2015 conference to detect depression and other mental health disorders among subjects using Twitter posts achieved promising results using topic modeling and rule-based methods [21-23].

Fewer works have focused on early detection of depression. Ophir, Asterhan and Schwarz [24] examined signals of depression among adolescent Facebook users with the aim of ultimately applying their coding scheme to early detection methods. De Choudhury et al. [9] achieved 70% accuracy in an experiment that compared scores on the Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale Revised (CES-D) [25] and Beck's Depression Inventory (BDI) [26] with Twitter users' engagement patterns and linguistic markers preceding a recent episode of depression to devise a

tool for predicting and measuring MDD in individuals. This study identified several distinctive features of posting activity associated with the onset of depression, such as diurnal cycles, more negative emotions, less social interaction, more self-focus, and more mentions of depression-related terms. However, as with most other research that attempts to predict depression, the analysis was dependent on self-reported cases, and to-date, approaches aiming to identify individuals who are as yet unaware of their depression diagnosis remain rare [18].

Our work is directly related to the Conference and Labs for the Evaluation Forum (CLEF) Lab on Early Risk Prediction on the Internet (eRisk) 2017 [27], during which the authors proposed a task on the early detection of depression with a time-aware methodology and using effectiveness metrics. In general, participants based their approaches on lexical, linguistic, semantic or statistical features, among others. We followed the workshop methodology [27-28] and used the best performing methods as baselines [29-30]. Trotzek et al. [29] based their model on linguistic meta-information extracted from the subjects' writings and developed a classifier using recurrent neural networks, whereas Villegas et al. [30] explicitly modelled partial information from the semantic representation of documents using learning algorithms such as Random Forest (RF) or Naive Bayes. Our work diverges from other approaches in being a dual model proposal, as well as in terms of the specific writing features analyzed.

Methods

Data analysis

Our input comprised a set of posts and comments from a social network, specifically gathered for the eRisk 2017 [28]. Data were extracted from Reddit using the Reddit's application program interface (API), and the resulting dataset consists of a collection of tuples of the form (id, writing), such that "id" is a unique identifier for each social network user and "writing" represents a writing instance in the social network. At the same time, each writing was described as a tuple of the form (title, date, info, text), whereby "title" indicates the title of the post or comment, "date" denotes the date and time when the writing was performed, "info" identifies the social network (in this case, only Reddit is considered), and "text" comprises the actual post or comment provided by the user.

Depressed users are identified searching for self-reports of depression diagnoses in their posts. Moreover, a manual review is performed to verify that posts were genuine [28]. Then, a control group is created by randomly selecting a large set of redditors, including some individuals who were active on the depression subreddit but had no depression diagnosed.

The controls have not been checked for other diseases. The dataset has been formed starting from those writings where users claimed that they were depressed [28]. From there, a period of about a year has been considered for each user. The

intervals can differ because the maximum amount of submissions that can be retrieved per redditor is 2000 (Reddit's API limit).

As shown in Table 1, the dataset includes a total of 887 subjects, of which 135 have been diagnosed with depression, and encompasses more than 500,000 different posts and comments, with an average of nearly 600 posts per subject.

Table 1. Analysis dataset statistics.

	Depressed	Control	Total
# subjects	135	752	887
# posts	49,557	481,837	531,394
Avg. submissions per subject	367.1	640.7	599.1
Avg. words per submission	27.3	21.9	22.4

Based on this data, we focused on estimating the likelihood that a particular subject could be considered depressed given his/her particular social network posts.

Subject behavior

To characterize subject's behavior on the dataset, we performed a detailed analysis of the main characteristics that might have an impact on the early detection of depression. We concentrated on variables that could be easily measured directly from the writings and that we expected to capture some differences in behavior between both types of subjects.

Textual spreading

We began our analysis by characterizing the textual spreading of the writings produced by the subjects by measuring the number of words used in each of the writings. Figure 1 shows the words used in the posts titles, both for depressed and non-depressed individuals. It becomes apparent to an observer that the number of titles with zero words is significantly higher among the depressed users. That can be explained by considering how Reddit users can publish new writings: they can either publish a new reddit, for which it is mandatory to add a title; or they can comment an already existing reddit. Thus, these results led us to conclude that depressed users have a higher tendency to reply to existing issues rather than publish new ones.

On the other hand, analyzing the second plot in Figure 1, we can observe how the non-depressed users tended to send many more writings with zero words in their content description, while depressed subjects tended to elaborate more on their writings. In fact, the percentage of posts using between 11 and 100 words is nearly 14 points higher for depressed subjects, and it nearly doubles the percentage for even larger posts (more than one hundred words). To better understand this

analysis, it is important to note that there are two kinds of new submissions in Reddit: text submissions, whereby a user can add a text description to his/her title; and link submissions, in which in which text descriptions cannot be added, thus producing zero words in the text field.

The third plot in Figure 1 demonstrates that the total textual spreading of writings is similar for both depressed and non-depressed subjects. Although there are clear differences between the ways that depressed and non-depressed users submitted their writings, the differences in the titles are compensated for by the differences in the text, which results in similar distributions taking into account the total number of words. In any case, it is noticeable that the depressed individuals tended to elaborate their writings more and use more overall words than those who were not depressed.

Time gap

Next, we focused on the time gap between two consecutive writings. Figure 2 displays a density plot for the time gap between writings for depressed and non-depressed individuals. From the figure we can observe a higher mean among the depressed subjects, taking more time between two consecutive writings. In fact, the average time spent for a depressed subject between two writings is five days (5.076), while non-depressed writers will post again one day faster (4.037). Also significant are the differences in the standard deviation, which is about eight days (8.330) for non-depressed, but rises to 11 days (11.048) for depressed subjects. This result suggests that depressed subjects exhibit higher variability in their publication routine on the social network. Both the mean and standard deviation were tested for equality between both subject types using standard two-sided t-test with significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, which confirmed significant differences between these values among depressed and non-depressed subjects.

Time span

We also explored the time span of the different writings in terms of the days and times of day when they were produced. The classification of writings according to the day of the week is described in the first plot in Figure 3. The main difference between both types is that non-depressed subjects tended to publish less during weekends than depressed individuals, whereas this tendency was inverted during weekdays, except on Mondays. The publication rate throughout the whole is more homogeneous for depressed individuals, although there is still a small reduction at weekends, while the non-depressed subjects exhibited a publication peak on Wednesdays, followed by a gradual reduction that reaches its lowest point during the weekend.

Finally, the second plot in Figure 3 shows how depressed subjects tended to send more posts and comments than non-depressed users over the hours from midnight to midday, whereas the latter published more in the afternoon. The main differences appear six hours before midday, when depressed subjects were most active, and six hours after, when non-depressed subjects were most active. The same behavior was

observed by Choudhury et al. [9], arguing that night time online activity is a known characteristic of these individuals, which may be the reason behind this increase.

Depression prediction

The depression prediction problem presented in this work can be formalized as a binary classification problem using the presence or absence of depression diagnosis as a label. Accordingly, to address this machine learning problem, we resorted to a features-based approach and design a collection of features that are expected to capture correlations between different aspects of the individual's writings and depression. We represented each training example by a feature vector: $\varphi(\text{id}, \text{writing}) \in \mathbb{R}^F$, where F denotes the number of features, and then we used this vector as input for the prediction function V . Using this approach enabled us to develop a large number of features, and we employed techniques suited for learning on a large scale, such as tree-based algorithms in order to estimate relationships between those features and depression. We propose three types of features: textual similarity, semantic similarity and writing features.

Textual similarity features

Positive subjects refer to those diagnosed with MDD and vice versa for negative subjects. The main goal of these features is to estimate the degree of alignment of a subject's writings with positive or negative subjects, which enables the researcher to estimate the similarity between a given subject versus positive and negative subjects. We ignored word ordering and opted for a bag-of-words representation that considered two different measures extensively used in the literature: cosine similarity and Okapi BM25. Each subject was represented as a document that included all his/her writings and was modeled as a collection of words: $d = \{w_1, \dots, w_l(d)\}$, where $l(d)$ represents the number of terms in the text.

The cosine similarity between two subjects q and d is calculated as in Singhal (2001):

$$\cos(q, d) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{l(q)} (IDF(q_i) \cdot cnt(q_i, q)) \cdot (IDF(d_i) \cdot cnt(d_i, d))}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{l(q)} (IDF(q_i) \cdot cnt(q_i, q))^2} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{l(d)} (IDF(d_i) \cdot cnt(d_i, d))^2}}$$

where $cnt(q_i, q)$ is the number of times that the term q_i appears in the document q and $IDF(q_i)$ is the inverse document frequency for term q_i that is computed over a corpus C as:

$$IDF(w; C) = \log \frac{n_{docs(C)} - n(w; C) + 0.5}{n(w; C) + 0.5},$$

where $n_{docs}(C)$ represents the overall number of documents in C (equivalent to the number of subjects), while $n(w; C)$ is the number of documents that contain the term w .

The Okapi BM25 similarity between two subjects q and d was scored as in Robertson and Zaragoza [32]:

$$BM25(q, d) = \sum_{i=1}^{l(q)} IDF(q_i) \frac{cnt(q_i, d) \cdot (k_1 + 1)}{cnt(q_i, d) + k_1(1 - b + b \cdot l(d)/\bar{l})}$$

where k_1 is a scaling factor for the term frequency, b is a scale factor on the document length and l is the average number of terms in a document. In our setting, each subject was represented by the concatenation of all the textual information available for each writing (title, info and text), and the IDF dictionary was computed over the overall collection of these documents. The textual similarity between two subjects might have different degrees of importance, and to address this effect, we also used the aggregation of cosine and BM25 scores, with each computed between the different parts of the textual information available.

For each subject, we aggregated the scores obtained for all his/her writings by calculating the average value, standard deviation, minimum, maximum and median. This process was repeated for both positive and negative samples and, in all cases, the active subject was removed from the samples.

Semantic similarity features

We applied Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) as one of the best known Vector Space Models (VSM) to capture semantic relationships among documents. LSA explicitly learns semantic word vectors by applying Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), which in turn projects the input word-representation into a lower-dimensional space of dimensionality $k \ll V$, where semantically related words are closer than unrelated words.

In LSA, a document-term matrix M was constructed from a given text base of n documents containing m terms. This matrix of size $m \times n$ was then decomposed via a singular value decomposition into three matrices: the term vector matrix T ; the document vector matrix D and the diagonal matrix S :

$$M = TSD^T$$

These matrices were then reduced to the given number of dimensions k to result into truncated matrices T_k , S_k and D_k creating the latent semantic space [33]:

$$M_k = \sum_{i=1}^k t_i \cdot s_i \cdot d_i^T$$

Different dimensionality methods have been tested in the literature. In order to compute the k dimensionality, this study typically used the Kaiser-Criterion [37], which will take values higher than 1.0 and return the number of singular values accordingly. We also tested the share dimensionality, which finds the first position in descending order of the singular values where their proportional sum meets or exceeds a specific share, and the fraction dimensionality, which takes a specific fraction of the number of singular values [38]; however, no relevant differences were identified among the different methods.

Semantic similarity features between two subjects were computed as the Euclidean distance between the respective projections into the embedding space. As described in Section 4.1, each subject was represented as a document that aggregated all of his/her writings. In this case, all the available textual information was used to compute the singular values. LSA was applied both following a full-text approach and removing stop words and using Porter stemming [34]. Finally, we applied feature scaling to normalize the LSA scores computed following min-max normalization [35]:

$$x' = \frac{x - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)}$$

where x is the original value and x' is the normalized value.

Writing features

The collection of features was used to profile the characteristics of the subjects' writings on the basis of the findings from Section 3. As reviewed above, we defined three signals: textual spreading, time gap and time span. Textual spreading measures the amount of textual information provided by the subject in his/her writings, and to address this feature, we introduced the following features:

- **NWritings**: the number of writings produced by the subject.
- **AvgWords**: the average number of words per writing. For each writing all the textual information available is considered.
- **DevWords**: standard deviation for the number of words per writing.
- **MinWords**: minimum number of words in the subject's writings.
- **MaxWords**: maximum number of words in the subject's writings.
- **MedWords**: median for the number of words in the subject's writing.

To measure the time elapsed between two consecutive writings, we aggregated the writings time gap information for each subject. In this way, if a subject only had one writing in the time period considered, the time gap would be zero. Otherwise, the time gap would measure the number of seconds between two consecutive writings. A logarithmic transformation of the raw time gap values was also considered, resulting in the following two sets of features:

- **TimeGap**: the aggregated information for the time lapse between two consecutive writings. These values are represented as the average, standard deviation, minimum, maximum and median.
- **LogTimeGap**: for the logarithmic transformation of the time gap values. The same aggregation values are computed for each subject.

Finally, another group of features was used to profile the moment when the writings were created by the subject. This information was expected to model differences in behavior among subjects diagnosed with depression versus those who had not been so diagnosed. The following time features were proposed:

- **Day**: percentage of writings provided by the subject, for each day of the week.
- **Weekday**: accumulative percentage for all writings created in a weekday.

- Weekend: accumulative percentage for all writings posted during the weekend.
- Hour: the hours of the day are divided in four homogeneous classes (0:00-5:59, 6:00-11:59, 12:00-17:59, 18:00-23:59) and the percentage of writings that fall into each class is calculated.

Models

We employed a readily available machine learning toolkit to develop a learning model incorporating the features that were identified. We considered RF [36] to be the most appropriate machine learning model to solve the classification problem. Learners' meta-parameters (number of trees, BM25's b and k_1) have been selected independently in an external development set.

The evaluation followed a time-aware methodology in which the writings were chronologically sorted and grouped into subsets. Each subset was evaluated independently, and the model was required to emit one of three possible decisions:

- Depression: the subject is considered to suffer from depression. This decision is final.
- Non-Depression: the subject is considered not to suffer from depression. This decision is final.
- No Decision: there is not enough evidence to produce a definitive decision and it is delayed.

As this is not a traditional binary classification problem due to the delay option available when processing the different subjects' writings, we proposed two different approaches: singleton and dual. The singleton model uses only one RF model, which is trained using the corresponding features, and a decision function is integrated to determine if enough evidence is available to proceed with a firm diagnosis or the decision must be delayed. The decision function was defined as $\delta(m, th_+(i), th_-(i))$, where m denotes the machine learning model used in the binary classification problem and $th_+(i)$ is a threshold function that sets a limit for a positive decision depending on the information chunk being processed (i), while $th_-(i)$ is a threshold function that sets a limit for a negative decision. Both threshold functions are not required to be the same, although they could be.

Different threshold functions were considered; however, the best performance was obtained with a decreasing step function. The steps of these threshold functions were tuned with a grid search over $\{0.95, 0.9, 0.85, 0.8, 0.75, 0.7, 0.65, 0.6, 0.55, 0.5\}$ on the training set, and selected the best performing steps for experimentation. Finally, both threshold functions (positive and negative) are the same and follow the equation:

$$th(i) = 0.9_{XA[1,0.9]} + 0.8_{XA[0.9,0.8]} + 0.7_{XA[0.8,0.7]} + 0.6_{XA[0.7,0.6]} + 0.5_{XA[0.6,0.5]}$$

where $XA(x)$ is the indicator function defined as:

$$XA(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{if } x \notin A \end{cases}$$

On the other hand, the dual model uses two RF models trained each one with an independent set of features. The first model (m_+) is trained to predict depression cases, while the second model (m_-) is trained to predict non-depression cases. For the dual model, a decision function of the form $\delta(m_+, m_-, th_w, th_+, th_-)$ was defined, where m_+ and m_- are the two learning models considered, th_w denotes the number of threshold writings and th_+ and th_- are the threshold functions applied to m_+ and m_- , respectively. Both threshold functions are defined as constant functions of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} th_+ &= 0.9 \\ th_- &= 0.5 \end{aligned}$$

The positive threshold function takes the upper step (0.9) from the positive threshold function of the singleton model, whereas the negative threshold function takes the lower step (0.5) of the negative threshold function of the singleton model.

In the dual model, if the number of writings is below th_w the first model is applied with decision threshold function th_+ , so that if a positive probability is above the threshold a depression decision is emitted, otherwise the decision is delayed. If the number of writings is above the writings threshold the second model is applied with decision threshold function th_- . In this case, if the non-depression probability is above the threshold the final decision is emitted and otherwise, the decision is delayed.

Results

Dataset

Table 2 presents the main statistics for the dataset. A total of 892 subjects were considered, of whom approximately 15% had been diagnosed with MDD. All submissions were collected from Reddit for a period covering more than a year [28]. Subjects with less than 10 submissions were removed.

Table 2. Dataset statistics.

	Training		Test	
	Depressed	Control	Depressed	Control
# subjects	83	403	52	349
# posts	30,851	264,172	18,706	217,665
Avg. submissions per subject	371.7	655.5	359.7	623.7
Avg. words per submission	27.6	21.3	26.9	22.5

The following evaluation is based on a subject based train-test split, as reported on Table 2, with an approximate percentage of 55% on the training set and 45% for testing.

The sequence of writings in the test set was chronologically sorted and the set was further divided into 10 subsets (or chunks), each of which contained 10% of the messages. These subsets were considered sequentially in such a manner that the first subset contained the oldest 10% messages, the second subset the second oldest 10% and so forth. This test subset division was a particularly important element in the evaluation, as its main objective was to detect, as soon as possible, a depression case, which would represent an improvement over traditional evaluation, which identifies cases without regard for speed. This becomes patent in the performance measure described in the next section.

Performance measure

Standard classification metrics such as precision, recall or F-measure do not take into account time and therefore we opt for the Early Risk Detection Error (ERDE) [28]. This measure will consider both the correctness of the decision and the delay taken by the model to make the decision, where the delay is measured by the number of writings (posts or comments) seen before providing an answer.

Given a decision (d) taken by the system with a delay (k) and a ground truth (gt) for each subject, the ERDE measure is defined as:

$$ERDE_o(d, k) = \begin{cases} c_{fp} & \text{if } d = \text{positive AND } gt = \text{negative} \\ c_{fn} & \text{if } d = \text{negative AND } gt = \text{positive} \\ lc_o(k) \cdot c_{tp} & \text{if } d = \text{positive AND } gt = \text{positive} \\ 0 & \text{if } d = \text{negative AND } gt = \text{negative} \end{cases}$$

where c_{fp} and c_{fn} are the cost associated with a false positive and false negative, respectively. In this work, following Losada and Crestani [28], c_{fn} was set to 1 and c_{fp} was set to the proportion of positive cases in the test dataset (i.e., 0.1296). The correct detection of a negative does not have any repercussion (negative nor positive) in the performance of the system, independently of the moment when it is detected, since this is considered a non-risk case that would not require an early intervention. In the case of a correct positive decision, the factor $lc_o(k)$ introduces a cost associated to the delay in detecting a true positive. As suggested by Losada and Crestani [28], $c_{tp} = c_{fn}$, as a late detection can have the same negative consequences as a false negative.

For the $lc_o(k)$ factor we use a monotonically increasing function of k :

$$lc_o(k) = 1 - \frac{1}{1 + \exp(k - o)}$$

For each subject, the ERDE metric was computed and a final score was obtained averaging all the ERDE values. Since all cost weights are in $[0, 1]$ then ERDE is also in the same range, and the quality of system performance increases as values approach

zero. Following the evaluation procedure on Losada and Crestani [28], ERDE₅ and ERDE₅₀ measures were used for a comparison with the baselines.

Baselines

Table 3 presents the main metrics for the baselines considered. The first three rows contain some naïve baseline methods, the middle rows show results for some Oracle methods and the last two rows expose the best performing methods from eRisk 2017 [28]. For all methods, we present the ERDE₅ and ERDE₅₀ metrics as the performance measures used in the eRisk 2017 competition, as well as F-measure (F1), Precision (P) and Recall (R).

Table 3: Baselines used for comparison with our proposed methods.

	ERDE ₅	ERDE ₅₀	F1	P	R
Random	18.51	15.20	0.20	0.12	0.00
All-depressed	21.67	15.03	0.23	0.13	1.00
Non-depressed	12.97	12.97	0.00	0.00	0.00
Oracle1	10.38	3.74	1.00	1.00	1.00
Oracle2	11.83	5.30	1.00	1.00	1.00
Oracle3	12.23	6.73	1.00	1.00	1.00
Oracle5	12.59	7.86	1.00	1.00	1.00
Oracle10	12.97	12.97	1.00	1.00	1.00
FHDOB	12.70	10.39	0.55	0.69	0.46
UNSLA	13.66	9.68	0.59	0.48	0.79

Three different naïve methods that do not require any specific features (textual, semantic or writing) were considered. The random strategy emits a random decision for each subject. As the evaluation is divided into 10 chunks, for each subject on each chunk this method randomly produces one of the three options ("depression", "non-depression" or "no decision") with equal probability. As soon as the system produces a diagnosis ("depression" or "non-depression") later decisions are not taken into account. The naïve all depressed method will emit a "depression" decision for all subjects for all chunks. As the first chunk provides a decision for all subjects, the actions in the following chunks do not have any repercussion in the system performance. In this case, the recall reached its maximum, as expected, although both ERDE metrics obtained modest results.

We also present the non-depressed method that emits a "non-depression" decision for all subjects. As observed in Table 3, this method scored zero in all effectiveness metrics. The Oracle methods present the results for an oracle that perfectly

diagnoses all subjects at the specified chunk (only results for chunks 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 are displayed). These results prove the difficulty of this task, as the effectiveness metrics (precision, recall and F-measure) obtained perfect values, whereas the ERDE metrics showed error values. Oracle10 obtained the same results for non-depression due to the strict penalization of late detection of depression cases (being equivalent to a wrong diagnosis of non-depression).

Finally, the best methods from eRisk 2017 were considered for both ERDE₅ and ERDE₅₀. The FHDOB method was presented by the Biomedical Computer Science Group from the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Dortmund (Germany). This model employed linguistic meta-information extracted from the subjects' texts and considered classifiers based on bag of words, paragraph vector, latent semantic analysis (LSA), and recurrent neural networks using long short term memory [29]. The UNSLA method was presented by the LIDIC Research Group from the Universidad Nacional de San Luis (Argentina). This method is based on a semantic representation of documents that explicitly considers the partial information available in different chunks of data, complemented with standard categorization technology. In this case, predictions are based on their own temporal models and other sources of opinion. The LIDIC group considered multiple document representations (bag of words, concise semantic analysis, character 3-grams, linguistic inquiry and word count features) and different learning algorithms, including RF, Naive Bayes, and decision trees [30].

An important difference between ERDE₅ and ERDE₅₀ is that the former promotes methods that emit few yet rapid depression decisions, while the latter gives smoother penalties to delays. ERDE₅ from FHDOB and ERDE₅₀ from UNSLA were used as main baselines for the comparison of our proposed methods.

Evaluation

In this section, we present our main findings for the classification task described and we discuss the effects of features and the performance for the different proposed models.

The first set of experiments was focused on the singleton model (Table 4). Initially we tested the performance of textual and standalone LSA features, finding very low performance on the semantic features, compared to textual features. The normalization of the LSA scores slightly improved the results and the use of stemming and stop words removal had a negative impact on performance, as shown by the zero values on precision, recall and F-measure for normalized LSA with stemming. The best performance among textual features was obtained by BM25 using all textual writing fields (title, info and text).

Next, we analyzed the performance of textual features combined with the writing features, as defined in Section 4.3. Curiously, BM25 performance worsened as the writing features were included, whereas cosine performance improved. However,

the best results were obtained combining both textual features (cosine and BM25 similarity) with the writing features using all textual writing fields.

Table 4: Evaluation results for the singleton model on different feature sets. WF groups all writing features presented. The values for the best ERDE with $\alpha = 5$ and $\alpha = 50$ are in italics.

	ERDE ₅	ERDE ₅₀	F1	P	R
Cos Text	15.83	13.22	0.31	0.23	0.46
Cos All	16.48	13.62	0.36	0.24	0.67
BM25 Text	18.11	16.61	0.26	0.16	0.60
BM25 All	14.36	12.43	0.36	0.32	0.40
LSA	21.60	14.96	0.23	0.13	1.00
Norm LSA	21.34	18.02	0.23	0.13	1.00
LSA stem	23.51	14.70	0.23	0.13	1.00
Norm LSA stem	12.97	12.97	0.00	0.00	0.00
Cos Text + WF	14.09	13.60	0.07	0.33	0.04
Cos All + WF	13.31	12.31	0.20	0.67	0.12
BM25 Text + WF	15.59	14.62	0.29	0.24	0.37
BM25 All + WF	20.49	18.05	0.30	0.18	0.83
Cos BM25 Text + WF	14.15	12.97	0.3	0.38	0.25
Cos BM25 All + WF	13.29	12.97	0.12	0.29	0.08
LSA Cos Text + WF	17.86	12.92	0.29	0.18	0.73
LSA BM25 Text + WF	16.61	12.09	0.27	0.18	0.56
LSA Cos All + WF	19.51	13.46	0.26	0.15	0.90
LSA BM25 All + WF	20.47	14.08	0.24	0.14	0.94
LSA Cos BM25 Text + WF	18.34	12.85	0.28	0.17	0.85
LSA Cos BM25 All + WF	<i>12.89</i>	<i>11.27</i>	0.34	0.45	0.27
Norm LSA Cos Text + WF	13.35	13.35	0.04	0.20	0.02
Norm LSA BM25 Text + WF	13.58	13.33	0.11	0.17	0.08
Norm LSA Cos All + WF	14.70	14.45	0.11	0.21	0.08
Norm LSA BM25 All + WF	14.55	14.30	0.13	0.22	0.10
Norm LSA Cos BM25 Text + WF	14.60	14.60	0.25	0.25	0.08
Norm LSA Cos BM25 All + WF	13.73	13.48	0.20	0.20	0.08

Subsequently, the three feature types were combined (textual, semantic, writings), and the best performance result for these experiments was obtained when the textual similarity metrics (cosine and BM25) used all textual fields, altogether with LSA and writing features. The same set of experiments was executed with normalized LSA and, although the results generally improved, they did not outperform the best value for non-normalized LSA. Focusing on the best performing singleton model from Table 4, we individually analyzed the results for the different writing features described on Section 4.3 in order to determine these features' behavior. Table 5 shows the results, highlighting the best $ERDE_5$ and $ERDE_{50}$ values. Best Singleton Model (BSM) refers to *LSA Cos BM25 All* and the writing features are grouped in the following manner:

- Writing: NWritings, AvgWords, DevWords, MinWords, MaxWords, MedWords.
- TimeGap
- LogTimeGap
- Day
- Week: Weekday, Weekend
- Hour

Regarding a fast early detection (measured through $ERDE_5$), the best performance was obtained just considering the text features, the time gap between writings and the publication days, which closely reflected the conclusions extracted from our data analysis on Section 3 in that a higher tendency to publish during the weekends could be observed in the depressed group. Relatively good results were also obtained combining textual features with the log time gap and writing hours (second best performance). Curiously, the combination of both week group and hour with textual features and time gap led to the worst results of the group. However, the best $ERDE_5$ value from Table 4 was not outperformed by any combination, as each of these features is expected to capture different variables in the writings' behavior.

The best value from the $ERDE_{50}$ metric was obtained by combining text features, both time gap variants and the publication days. Three of these features obtained the best $ERDE_5$ performance on Table 5. In this case, $ERDE_{50}$ outperformed the best value from Table 4, although values are extremely close (11.26 and 11.27, respectively).

The performance values obtained on Tables 4 and 5 do not outperform the performance from our baselines, although the results are closer in the case of $ERDE_5$.

Table 5. Evaluation results for classification on different writings features for the best singleton model (BSM) from Table 4, which combines cosine and BM25 textual features for all text fields and LSA features. The values for the best ERDE with $\alpha=5$ and $\alpha=50$ are in italics.

	ERDE ₅	ERDE ₅₀	F1	P	R
BSM + Writing, TimeGap, Hour	17.35	11.39	0.30	0.18	0.85
BSM + Writing, TimeGap, Day	<i>13.59</i>	12.12	0.22	0.31	0.17
BSM + Writing, TimeGap, Week	14.77	11.44	0.33	0.25	0.48
BSM + Writing, LogTimeGap, Hour	14.03	13.54	0.12	0.29	0.08
BSM + Writing, LogTimeGap, Day	18.95	12.53	0.27	0.16	0.96
BSM + Writing, LogTimeGap, Week	17.80	12.72	0.28	0.17	0.85
BSM + Writing, TimeGap, Day, Hour	16.14	11.55	0.31	0.21	0.63
BSM + Writing, TimeGap, Week, Hour	19.28	12.85	0.26	0.15	0.94
BSM + Writing, LogTimeGap, Day, Hour	16.86	12.28	0.29	0.18	0.77
BSM + Writing, LogTimeGap, Week, Hour	16.91	12.13	0.29	0.19	0.63
BSM + Writing, TimeGap, LogTimeGap, Day	17.00	<i>11.26</i>	0.31	0.19	0.87
BSM + Writing, TimeGap, LogTimeGap, Week	17.85	12.62	0.30	0.18	0.87
BSM + Writing, TimeGap, LogTimeGap, Hour	17.71	12.65	0.28	0.17	0.83
BSM + Writing, TimeGap, LogTimeGap, Hour, Week	16.53	13.47	0.29	0.20	0.52

Tables 6 and 7 show the performance results in terms of ERDE₅ and ERDE₅₀ for different dual model configurations. In the case of the dual model, two models were trained in parallel: one to detect depression cases (positive) and another to detect non-depression cases (negative). Both tables show a matrix in which the first column indicates the different features considered for the positive model, and the first row provides the features for the negative model (in the same order as the positive features).

Experiments were performed with an extensive number of feature combinations, but we have limited the results displayed on the tables to the most relevant performing features. Focusing on ERDE₅ (Table 6), the best results were obtained when using textual features (both cosine and BM25 similarity metrics) only for the text field, LSA and writing features on the positive model, combined with LSA variants or textual features for the negative model. Among the LSA variants, except for plain LSA, normalized LSA, LSA with stemming and normalized LSA with stemming provide the best performance. The sole use of textual similarity features (feature sets 5 and 6) with any LSA features leads to a best performing model.

We also report on statistical significance using a standard two-sided t-test with significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ when improving performance of the best singleton model on Table 4. Significant improvements over the best singleton model were obtained with positive models using both textual features (cosine and BM25) in all fields or just the text field, combined with semantic and writing features, as well as negative models based on LSA (normalized, stemming and both) or both textual features with writing features (but skipping LSA). This suggests that all the proposed features are required to provide an early risk detection for the identification of depressed subjects, whereas a less complex model achieves better results in identifying non-depressed subjects.

Table 6. Evaluation results for classification on different feature sets for the dual model ($th_w = 6$). The first column shows features for the positive model, and the first row shows features for the negative model. Positive feature sets are numbered and negative features follow the same numbering. Statistically significant performance improvements over the best singleton model on Table 4 are marked with †. The values for the best ERDE₅ are in italics.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
LSA (1)												
	13.24	12.99	12.99	12.99	12.99	12.99	13.48	13.24	13.48	13.24	29.20	13.24
Norm LSA (2)												
	13.22	12.97	12.97	12.97	13.47	12.97	13.47	13.22	13.47	13.22	29.43	13.22
LSA stem (3)												
	13.40	13.15	13.15	13.15	13.15	13.15	13.65	13.40	13.65	13.40	29.36	13.40
Norm LSA stem (4)												
	13.22	12.97	12.97	12.97	13.47	12.97	13.47	13.22	13.47	13.22	29.43	13.22
Cos BM25 Text + WF (5)												
	13.22	12.97	12.97	12.97	13.47	12.97	13.47	13.22	13.47	13.22	29.43	13.22
Cos BM25 All + WF (6)												
	13.22	12.97	12.97	12.97	13.47	12.97	13.47	13.22	13.47	13.22	29.43	13.22
LSA Cos Text + WF (7)												
	13.24	12.99	12.99	12.99	12.99	12.99	13.48	13.24	13.48	13.24	29.20	13.24
LSA BM25 Text + WF (8)												
	13.24	12.99	12.99	12.99	12.99	12.99	13.48	13.24	13.48	13.24	29.20	13.24
LSA Cos All + WF (9)												
	12.14	11.89	11.89	11.89	11.89	11.89	12.39	12.14	12.39	12.14	28.35	12.14
LSA BM25 All + WF (10)												
	13.24	12.99	12.99	12.99	12.99	12.99	13.48	13.24	13.48	13.24	29.20	13.24
LSA Cos BM25 Text + WF (11)												
	12.13	<i>11.88†</i>	<i>11.88†</i>	<i>11.88†</i>	<i>11.88†</i>	<i>11.88†</i>	12.38	12.13	12.38	12.13	28.34	12.13
LSA Cos BM25 All + WF (12)												
	12.73	12.49†	12.49†	12.49†	12.73	12.49†	12.98	12.73	12.98	12.73	28.94	12.73

Table 7. Evaluation results for classification on different feature sets for the dual model ($th_w = 53$). The first column shows features for the positive model, and the first row shows features for the negative model. Positive feature sets are numbered and negative features follow the same numbering. Statistically significant performance improvements over the best singleton model on Table 4 are marked with †. The values for the best ERDE₅₀ are in italics.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
LSA (1)												
	10.20	9.95	9.95	9.95	9.95	9.95	10.45	10.20	10.45	9.95	16.18	10.20
Norm LSA (2)												
	15.46	15.21	12.97	15.21	15.21	15.21	15.71	15.46	15.71	15.46	31.42	15.46
LSA stem (3)												
	11.19	10.94	10.94	10.94	10.94	10.94	11.44	11.19	11.44	11.19	25.15	11.19
Norm LSA stem (4)												
	15.46	15.21	12.97	15.21	15.21	15.21	15.71	15.46	15.71	15.46	31.42	15.46
Cos BM25 Text + WF (5)												
	15.46	15.21	12.97	15.21	15.21	15.21	15.71	15.46	15.71	15.46	31.42	15.46
Cos BM25 All + WF (6)												
	15.46	15.21	12.97	15.21	15.21	15.21	15.71	15.46	15.71	15.46	31.42	15.46
LSA Cos Text + WF (7)												
	10.20	9.95†	9.95†	9.95†	9.95†	9.95†	10.45	10.20	10.45	9.95†	16.18	10.20†
LSA BM25 Text + WF (8)												
	10.20	9.95†	9.95†	9.95†	9.95†	9.95†	10.45	10.20	10.45	9.95†	16.18	10.20†
LSA Cos All + WF (9)												
	10.41	10.16	9.16	10.16	10.16	10.16	10.66	10.41	10.66	10.16	16.65	10.41
LSA BM25 All + WF (10)												
	10.32	10.07	10.07	10.07	10.07	10.07	10.57	10.32	10.57	10.07	16.30	10.32
LSA Cos BM25 Text + WF (11)												
	10.17	9.93	<i>8.68†</i>	9.93	9.93	9.93	10.42	10.17	10.42	9.93	17.41	10.17
LSA Cos BM25 All + WF (12)												
	13.48	13.23	10.98†	13.23	13.23	13.23	13.73	13.48	13.73	13.48	28.94	13.48

Results for ERDE₅₀ (Table 7) are consistent with ERDE₅ performance, but the optimal value is limited to the positive model with textual features on the text field, LSA and writing features, while the negative model only applies LSA with stemming and removing stop words. Other best performing models from Table 6 obtained the third best performance for ERDE₅₀, while second best uses cosine similarity for all text fields, LSA and writings features for the positive model. It is remarkable that negative model for both first and second best performance is based only on LSA with stemming and removing stop words. The dual model is able to clearly outperform the best baseline values for ERDE₅ and ERDE₅₀ from Table 3, with an improvement of 6.5% on ERDE₅ and more than 10% improvement on ERDE₅₀ over the best performing models on the state-of-the-art. Thus, we were able to improve on two different and independent best-performing models by employing a single model with two different configurations.

Discussion

In this paper, we presented two methods based on artificial intelligence that exclusively use data from social media networks to provide an early detection of depression cases. The problem was formalized as a classification problem and was addressed using machine learning. We resorted to a features-based approach and

designed a collection of features (textual, semantic and writing) that captured correlations between different aspects of the individuals' writings and depression.

Our best performing method was based on a dual approach, using a machine learning model to detect depressed subjects and another one to identify non-depressed ones. We conducted a thorough evaluation following a time-aware approach that rewards early detections and our results showed how the dual model improved state-of-the-art detection models more than 10%. We consider that these results can help in the development of new tools to identify at-risk individuals, enabling those people suffering from depression to detect and receive treatment as soon as possible.

This work can be extended in several ways. First, we would like to extend the set of features with other document representations. Secondly, we plan to study different model combinations for our dual approach with an intense focus on new machine learning algorithms and feature sets. Finally, we plan to evaluate the effectiveness of our models on different environments, such as information technologies or economics.

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Conflicts of Interest

None declared.

Abbreviations

API: application program interface

BSM: Best Singleton Model

CLEF: Conference and Labs for the Evaluation Forum

IDF: Inverse Document Frequency

LSA: Latent Semantic Analysis

ERDE: Early Risk Detection Error

eRisk: Early Risk Prediction on the Internet

MDD: Major Depressive Disorder

RF: Random Forest

WF: writing features

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Figure 1. Relative percentage for number of words used on title (a), text (b) and both fields (c) for depressed and non-depressed subjects.

Figure 2. Average time gaps distribution between writings for depressed and non-depressed subjects.

Figure 3. Time span bar plots according to the day of the week (a) and hour of the day (b) for depressed and non-depressed subjects.

